

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_4_2_3	
Title	Environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding for biodiversity assessments and biomonitoring.
Category	Environmental.
Purpose of the method	eDNA metabarcoding allows for a fast and reliable description of the biological communities' composition, as well as their genetic and spatial variation, in different ecosystems, opening for more rapid and reliable biodiversity assessment and monitoring programs.
Effort in time	Usually, the time required for one investigation depends on the experimental design defined
Number of objects investigated	Usually, the minimum number of samples is identified depending on the experimental design defined.
Data format	Qualitative, quantitative.
Description	<p>eDNA metabarcoding refers to the analysis of DNA molecules present in an environmental sample, such as water or sediment, through the PCR amplification of specific gene markers, high-throughput sequencing of amplicons, and taxonomic classification of DNA sequences comparing them with DNA barcodes deposited in the barcode reference databases.</p> <p>The high-throughput sequencing results are processed through bioinformatic pipelines developed in different programming languages (e.g., R, Python, etc.). The biodiversity results are tabulated (e.g., in Microsoft Excel ®) and processed with the use of statistical software (e.g., R for statistics).</p>
Basic Literature	<p>Pawlowski, J., Kelly-Quinn, M., Altermatt, F., Apothéloz-Perret-Gentil, L., Beja, P., Boggero, A., ... & Kahlert, M. (2018). The future of biotic indices in the ecogenomic era: Integrating (e) DNA metabarcoding in biological assessment of aquatic ecosystems. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i>, 637, 1295-1310. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.05.002</p> <p>Pinna, M., Zangaro, F., & Specchia, V. (2024). Assessing benthic macroinvertebrate communities' spatial heterogeneity in Mediterranean transitional waters through eDNA metabarcoding. <i>Scientific Reports</i>, 14(1), 17890. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-69043-w</p> <p>Shea, M. M., & Boehm, A. B. (2024). Environmental DNA metabarcoding differentiates between micro-habitats within the rocky intertidal. <i>Environmental DNA</i>, 6, e521. https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.521</p> <p>Specchia, V., Zangaro, F., Tzafesta, E., Saccomanno, B., Vadrucci, M. R., & Pinna, M. (2023). Environmental DNA detects biodiversity and ecological features of</p>

	<p>phytoplankton communities in Mediterranean transitional waters. Scientific Reports, 13(1), 15192. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-42389-3</p> <p>Specchia, V., Saccomanno, B., Zangaro, F., Tzafesta, E., & Pinna, M. (2022). Exploring the biodiversity of a European Natura 2000 Mediterranean lagoon through eDNA metabarcoding. Diversity, 14(11), 991. https://doi.org/10.3390/d14110991</p>
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